

Information Pricing

Mengxiao Zhang

Information Systems Department, University of Auckland Business School

mengxiao.zhang@auckland.ac.nz

¹Fernando Beltrán (Supervisor)

ABSTRACT

The rapid development of Web 2.0, IoT, Cloud Computing and other novel technologies has promoted the data creation, storage and transmission and the information extraction over the last years. Larger, faster and more varied information create economic, social and environmental value and it is traded as a good. Realizing the great value and commoditization of information, a information broker or intermediary provides a virtual platform, called data marketplace (examples of which are InfoChimps, Factual, Xignite, Microsoft Azure) and designed to facilitate the transactions of data and data-related services. Data marketplace is a two-sided platform whereby data and data-related services can be traded between two interested sides and the surplus is generated when the two sides interact. Economic literature has built a powerful sock of knowledge on two-sided markets but to the best of our knowledge, these researches have not attempted any platform data service pricing analysis using the two-sided market approach. Motivated by this, we analyze information-pricing methods in a two-sided context. Besides, we also consider the heterogeneity of data demanders and differentiated prices. This research study how the prices for two sides of the data market are affected by (1) cross-group externalities, (2) costs, (3) usage-based pricing, flat-fee model, or two-part tariff.

Keywords: data marketplaces, information pricing, two-sided markets.

INTRODUCTION

Data are symbols that are not necessarily of significance while information are processed data with a certain purpose (Ackoff, 1989). The rapid development of Web 2.0, IoT, Cloud

Computing and other novel technologies have promoted the data creation, storage and transmission and the information extraction over the last years. Some people, organizations and instrumented machinery can produce data every second. Through his activities, the “walking” individual is a constant source of data. For example, health data, web browsing data and location information are created when people are doing sports, shopping online and using GPSs. Some organizations also produce data, such as scientific data, experimental data and computed data. In addition, because of the emergence of IoT, sensor data produced by digital equipment, fitness devices and machines now become a significant part of information. The large amount of information is perceived as a new asset in the digital world.

Larger, faster and more varied information positively affects individuals, businesses and government and create economic, social and environmental value. For example, economic value accrues to businesses from leaner processes and production, better customer interactions, more targeted advertising and increased revenue. More information can improve government services, which lifts people’s wellbeing and creates social value¹.

Because of the increasing value of information and its wide availability, private and public sectors commonly purchase information from third parties. Realizing the great value and commoditization of information, a data broker or intermediary provides a virtual platform, called data marketplace (examples of which are InfoChimps, Factual, Xignite, Microsoft Azure) and designed to facilitate the transactions of data and data-related services. Such platform can be regarded as a two-sided market where two sides who are interested in data trade interact and the surplus is generated.

A data transaction involves four main actors: data creator, data demander, service provider, and market maker. Data creators are data sources and generate raw data. Service providers collect, process, store data and then provide data and data-related services to data demanders on online platforms via Internet. On a data marketplace, all participants need to consider the value of data in order to ensure a fair and sustainable market place for every involved party. Some pricing methods are used in practice, including free, usage-based pricing, package pricing, flat-fee tariff, two-part tariff and freemium (Muschalle, Stahl, Löser, & Vossen, 2012).

¹ <http://www.datafutures.co.nz/assets/Uploads/DF-Final-Report-4.pdf>

However, to the best of our knowledge, the existing research on information pricing has not attempted a data platform pricing analysis using the two-sided market approach. In this article, we analyze information-pricing methods in a two-sided context and study how discriminatory prices on the two sides of the data market are affected by (1) cross-group externalities, (2) different costs, (3) usage-based pricing, flat-fee model, or two-part tariff.

The paper is organized as follows. The Section 1 illustrates background information of data marketplaces and highlights the main issues to be investigated. The Section 2 reviews relevant literature and Section 3 describes the proposed method. Conclusions are reported in Section 4.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Data marketplace is a two-sided platform whereby data and data-related services can be traded between two interested sides and the surplus is generated when the two sides interact. For example, one data set might be of low value, but a combination of various data sources can create more value. Given that, data demanders prefer a data platform with more data service providers offering various data sources, while a data service provider is willing to join a platform with a greater number of data demanders. Economic literature has built a powerful stock of knowledge on two-sided markets but to the best of our knowledge, the existing research has not attempted any platform data service pricing analysis using the two-sided market approach. Motivated by this, we analyze information-pricing methods in a two-sided context.

J.-C. Rochet and Tirole (2004) defined two-sided markets as markets that involve two groups of end-users and try to attract the two groups “on board” by setting appropriate prices. There are many examples of two-sided markets, such as dating agencies or nightclubs, credit card industry, television channels and shopping malls. And there are many researches on such markets. Armstrong (2006) studied three main factors determining the prices for two groups, including extent of the cross-group externalities, fixed fees or per-transaction basis and single-homing or multi-homing and they investigated their findings in media platforms and supermarkets. Anderson and Coate (2005) considered the advertising provision and found that the nuisance cost to viewers, the substitutability of programs, and the expected benefits to advertisers determine the advertising level. J. C. Rochet and Tirole (2008) analyzed the impact of honor-all-cards rule in payment card associations and found that this rule can both benefit the platform and increase social welfare.

Price discrimination is often used in one-sided markets in order to increase market coverage and profit. However, it is seldom mentioned in research on two-sided markets. Caillaud and Jullien (2003) and Armstrong (2006) allow for different prices for each group of agents, but the prices within each group is same. Liu and Serfes (2013) considered perfect price discrimination on both sides while Angelucci, Cage, and de Nijs (2013) investigated second-degree price discrimination in the newspaper industry.

A question worth investigating is how the two-sidedness of the industry affects the scope for price discrimination. This research study three main factors determining the differentiated prices.

- Cross-group externalities. It means that the utilities of data demanders and data service providers could be influenced by the performance of the other side. The intensity of externality of each side can influence the prices.
- Different costs. Like any other good that is traded, costs are incurred in the process of obtaining information; in particular, a significant investment in infrastructure construction is needed at first, followed by further costs to operate the platform.
- Usage-based pricing, flat-fee model, and two-part tariff. These three pricing methods are widely used in practise. In usage models, data demanders pay for data services based on the amount of usage. In flat-fee models, data demanders pay a monthly subscription fee and have an unfettered access to services in return. In two-part-tariff models, consumers pay a fixed basic fee for a certain amount of usage and an additional fee when their usage exceed some pre-defined quota. (Muschalle et al., 2012)

METHODOLOGY

We build a model of price discrimination for a platform. In this model, three pricing methods (including usage-based pricing, flat-fee model and two-part tariff) are considered. Data demanders are heterogeneous in their preferences (e.g. usage count), they can purchase information by subscription, two-part-tariff, or on a usage basis. When setting the prices, market maker needs to take the heterogeneity of data demanders into account, aside from the various marginal costs and network externalities.

By solving the model as described above, the optimal price in each pricing framework can be derived. Then we compare the results derived in two-sided markets with that in one-sided markets and we intend to provide new managerial implications.

CONCLUSIONS

Data marketplaces commodify information and facilitate the transactions of data and data-related services. A data marketplace is a two-sided platform whereby data and data-related services can be traded between two interested sides and the surplus is generated when the two sides interact. Considering this, we analyze information-pricing methods in a two-sided context, this is the first contribution of this research. Beside, This research study how the differentiated prices for two sides of the data market are affected by (1) cross-group externalities, (2) costs, (3) usage-based pricing, flat-fee model, or two-part tariff. In a digital market platform, we consider the characteristics of information and obtain new results.

REFERENCES

- Ackoff, R. L. (1989). From data to wisdom. *Journal of applied systems analysis*, 16(1), 3-9.
- Anderson, S. P., & Coate, S. (2005). Market provision of broadcasting: A welfare analysis. *The review of Economic studies*, 72(4), 947-972.
- Angelucci, C., Cage, J., & de Nijs, R. (2013). *Price discrimination in a two-sided market: Theory and evidence from the newspaper industry*.
- Armstrong, M. (2006). Competition in two - sided markets. *The RAND Journal of Economics*, 37(3), 668-691.
- Caillaud, B., & Jullien, B. (2003). Chicken & egg: Competition among intermediation service providers. *RAND journal of Economics*, 309-328.
- Liu, Q., & Serfes, K. (2013). Price Discrimination in Two - Sided Markets. *Journal of Economics & Management Strategy*, 22(4), 768-786.
- Muschalle, A., Stahl, F., Löser, A., & Vossen, G. (2012). *Pricing approaches for data markets*. Paper presented at the International Workshop on Business Intelligence for the Real-Time Enterprise.
- Rochet, J.-C., & Tirole, J. (2004). *Defining two-sided markets*. mimeo, IDEI, Toulouse, France, January.
- Rochet, J. C., & Tirole, J. (2008). Tying in two-sided markets and the honor all cards rule. *International Journal of Industrial Organization*, 26(6), 1333-1347.